

HORIZON JU Research and Innovation Actions
HORIZON-EUROHPC-JU-2021-COE-01-01
European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking

Plasma Exascale-Performance Simulations CoE
101093261

D6.2
Report on Dissemination, Community Building,
Collaborations, Training, and Exploitation

WP6: Dissemination, Community Building, Training and Exploitation

Date of preparation (latest version): 31/12/2023
Copyright© 2023 – 2027 The Plasma-PEPSC Consortium

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable Number	D6.2
Deliverable Name	Report on Dissemination, Community Building, Collaborations, Training, and Exploitation
Due Date	31/12/2023
Deliverable lead	IPP CAS
Authors	David Tskhakaya (IPP CAS), Ales Podolnik (IPP CAS) and Jeremy Williams (KTH)
Responsible Author	Tskhakaya (IPP CAS) E-mail: tskhakaya@ipp.cas.cz
Keywords	Collaboration, Dissemination Plan, Training Events, Community Building and Exploitation Plan
WP/Task	WP6/Task D6.2
Nature	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Final Version Date	31/12/2023
Reviewed by	Federica Bragone (KTH), Erwin Laure (MPG) and Pratibha Raghupat Hegde (KTH)

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Partner	Date	Comment	Version
IPP CAS	16/10/2023	First draft	0.1
IPP CAS	07/12/2023	Final draft	0.2
KTH	11/12/2023	Final draft updated for internal review	0.3
IPP CAS	18/12/2023	Revised draft after internal review	0.4
KTH	18/12/2023	Final cleanup for submission	1.0

Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we discuss the background, methodology and outcomes of project dissemination; present a list of the manuscripts submitted for publication in scientific journals and international conferences, where we had invited, oral and poster contributions in 2023; discuss the efforts made for community building, new collaborations and training sessions, which took place under the Plasma-PEPSC project during 2023. These indicate that dissemination, community building, collaborations, training, and exploitation activities performed are in agreement to project initial plans.

Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Dissemination	6
2.1	Website	6
2.2	Twitter/X	7
2.3	Scientific Publications	7
2.4	Presentations at Conferences and Workshops	9
2.5	Press Release	10
2.6	Awards	10
3	Collaboration with other CoEs and Castiel 2	11
4	Community Building	12
5	Training: Code Camp & Webinars	13
6	Exploitation	13
7	Conclusion	14

1 Introduction

The aim of the WP6 is to perform wide dissemination of the project outputs and achievements; to plan and contribute to the community building within the project and outside it; to strengthen existing and establish new collaborations in the research field as well as with other CoEs; to support organization of project meetings and training sessions. Special efforts to be directed towards increasing of user pools of the software developed under this project, as well as optimization of the high level support of such community.

The main aim of the dissemination activities is to disseminate project outcomes and maximize their impact. In these activities project members follow the main principles: awareness creation in the general public and decision makers, promotion of developed codes and other software to professional communities, knowledge transfer. Accordingly, dissemination activities are divided according to the target communities; e.g. for general public the main dissemination tools represent press releases, popular lectures, website and twitter account of the project. Dissemination to the plasma and HPC communities and industry is done mainly via contributions to scientific conferences, meetings and journal publications. These activities are supported by different code training sessions and by continuously nearing newly developed code access to the open-source software standards.

2 Dissemination

2.1 Website

The Plasma-PEPSC's website is utilized as the starting point for all dissemination activities, since it contains general information, important contacts, announcements and useful code repository information. The website has been created within 3 months after starting of the project and continuously updated during the first year to include additional material and content. Figure 1 shows a snapshot of site visitors in the last 12 months.

Figure 1: Plasma-PEPSC Website Visitor Snapshot.

2.2 Twitter/X

Plasma-PEPSC's Twitter account (<https://twitter.com/plasma-pepsc>) continues to play a large part in the project's dissemination strategy (see Figure 2). Figures 3 - 4 shows a recent tweet/post at SC23 Session Exhibits and Activity Analytics earned impressions per day in a 28 day period. The account has been used by researchers to promote events and disseminate talks they have given, or participated in, as well as news from the HPC community (Figure 1). Twitter has been an easy way of reaching out to the public by using a platform people trust and works side by side with Twitter's website. As of December 12, 2023, the number of Twitter followers is 22 (this number will be significantly increased in future).

Figure 2: Plasma-PEPSC Twitter/X page.

2.3 Scientific Publications

From January 1 2023 to July 2023 Plasma-PEPSC has published four open-access papers that are available online and are listed on the project's website.

1. Leveraging HPC Profiling & Tracing Tools to Understand the Performance of Particle-in-Cell Monte Carlo Simulations

Jeremy J. Williams, David Tskhakaya, Stefan Costea, Ivy B. Peng, Marta Garcia-Gasulla, and Stefano Markidis.

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2306.16512.pdf>

← Post

 Plasma-PEPSC - EuroHPC CoE for Plasma Simulations ...
@Plasma_PEPSC_EU

@Plasma_PEPSC_EU meets @EuroHPC_JU at SC23 (@Supercomputing)
Session Exhibit Booth 204 in Colorado Convention Center, Denver,
Colorado, USA
[#supercomputing](#) [#CentresofExcellence](#) [#Exascale](#) [#exascaleera](#)
[@HorizonEU](#)

10:13 PM · Nov 17, 2023 · 44 Views

Figure 3: Recent Tweet/Post on Twitter/X at SC23 Session Exhibits.

Your Tweets earned **146 impressions** over this **28 day** period

Figure 4: Recent Tweet/Post Activity Analytics on Twitter/X within a 28 day period.

2. MPI Performance Analysis in Vlasiator: Unraveling Communication Bottlenecks

Jennifer Faj, Jeremy J. Williams, Ivy Bo Peng, Urs Ganse, Markus Battarbee, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Leo Kotipalo, Minna Palmroth, and Stefano Markidis.

https://sc23.supercomputing.org/proceedings/tech_poster/poster_files/rpost127s3-file3.pdf

3. Enabling Quantum Computer Simulations on AMD GPUs: a HIP Backend for Google's qsim

Stefano Markidis.

<https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/3624062.3624223>

4. Quantum Computer Simulations at Warp Speed: Assessing the Impact of GPU Acceleration: A Case Study with IBM Qiskit Aer, Nvidia Thrust & cuQuantum.

Jennifer Faj, Ivy Peng, Jacob Wahlgren, and Stefano Markidis.

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2307.14860.pdf>

Currently, a scientific article by Jeremy J. Williams et al. on porting BIT1 to Optimized Multi-core CPU and GPU systems with OpenACC and OpenMP is under review.

2.4 Presentations at Conferences and Workshops

Results of our performance optimization and code development in Plasma-PEPSC have been presented at a number of HPC and application-oriented conferences including:

- PASC 2023, Mini-symposium (<https://pasc23.pasc-conference.org/program/minisymposia/>)
- ISC 2023, Birds of feather event (<https://app.swapcard.com/widget/event/is-c-high-performance-2023/planning/UGxhbm5pbmdfMTIyMDg0Mw==/>)
- EuroHPC Summit 2023, posters and presentations (<https://www.eurohpcsummit.eu/>)
- E-science Conference 2023 (<https://www.escience-conference.org/2023/>)
- EURO-PAR 2023 (<https://2023.euro-par.org/program/>)
- Cray User Group Conference, 2023 (<https://cug.org/cug-2023/>)
- Supercomputing, 2023 (<https://sc23.conference-program.com/>)

We had invited and oral presentations, as well as poster contributions. Accordingly we have submitted manuscripts to the proceedings as well refereed journal. Capabilities of our new tools was discussed also at leading fusion plasma theory conference EFTC 2023 (<https://indico.cern.ch/event/1239458/>).

We want to note that in our opinion, the current travel policies imposed severely limit our ability to disseminate project results; e.g. several activities presented here have had to be funded of through other means, and some others had to be cancelled at all.

2.5 Press Release

Plasma-PEPSC has a first press release¹ coordinated by KTH and its communication team (see Figure 5). The press release presented the profound societal impact of the project, highlighting its transformative potential. Specifically, emphasis was placed on the project's critical role in advancing clean energy through the development of fusion reactors. Additionally, it highlighted contributions to medical technology, particularly in the creation of compact accelerators with applications in cancer treatment.

[Denna sida på svenska](#)

Four codes that can change the future of energy use and cancer treatments

Plasma-PEPSC: A new centre of excellence for plasma simulations

Published Mar 14, 2023

Over the next four years, researchers at KTH will optimize four codes that can have significant impact on global energy use and the treatment of cancer patients. But competition is fierce between researchers in Europe, Japan, China and the US.

"We are looking into the future towards a new paradigm in large-scale plasma simulations", says [Stefano Markidis](#), Associate Professor of high-performance computing, when describing the EuroHPC Center of Excellence, a new four-year, European collaboration

Figure 5: First press release of the project on March 13, 2023.

2.6 Awards

Plasma-PEPSC has its first recipient of the ACM SIGHPC Computational and Data Science Fellowship for 2023 (see Figure 6). The ACM SIGHPC fellowships are highly

¹<https://www.kth.se/en/eecs/nyheter/fyra-koder-som-kan-forma-framtiden-inom-energi-och-cancervard-1.1238338>

competitive, and are awarded after a rigorous merit review. The nominations were evaluated and ranked by a panel of experts (who were themselves diverse with respect to race, gender, discipline, and nationality) based on nominees' overall potential for excellence in data science and/or computational science, and the extent to which they will serve as leaders and role models to increase diversity in the workplace. Jeremy J. Williams, Plasma-PEPSC Project Manager at KTH, was delighted to receive the award² and represent the project at SC23.

Figure 6: First Plasma-PEPSC recipient of the ACM SIGHPC fellowship at SC23.

3 Collaboration with other CoEs and Castiel 2

A separate activity was devoted to the collaboration with other CoEs; we strengthen collaboration with the Castiel 2³. The collaboration agreement with all beneficiaries will be signed imminently (till the end of 2023). In addition to the collaboration agreement, the Plasma-PEPSC members are actively engaged in Castiel 2 meetings (for instance the Plasma-PEPSC project has been presented at the Castiel 2 Training Coffee Break event on December 7, 2023) and providing input and feedback to the Castiel 2 deliverables.

In addition, we established a collaborative partnership with the SPACE EuroHPC CoE, a EuroHPC project dedicated to the development of plasma simulation codes with a specific focus on applications related to space and astrophysics. Our collaboration extended to joint initiatives, including the preparation of a shared poster showcased at the ISC2023 EuroHPC booth. Building on this cooperation, we are actively involved with SPACE in organizing for a collaborative workshop, entitled "Plasma Physics Towards

²<https://www.sighpc.org/for-your-career/fellowships/2023-fellowship-winners>

³[https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/eurocc-2-and-castiel-2-promoting-hpc-boost-digital-s kills-jobs-and-industrial-competitiveness-europe-2023-02-03_en](https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/eurocc-2-and-castiel-2-promoting-hpc-boost-digital-skills-jobs-and-industrial-competitiveness-europe-2023-02-03_en)

the ExaScale Era” at the HiPEAC Conference on January 19, 2024. The workshop will include several speakers from the Plasma-PEPSC project.

4 Community Building

As part of our community-building initiatives, Plasma-PEPSC coordinated a Birds of a Feather (BoF) session at ISC2023 in Hamburg, Germany, with a turnout of 35 attendees and 142 views on Twitter/X (see Figure 7). The primary objective was to bring together a diverse group comprising application experts in plasma simulations, computer scientists, and the broader computational plasma physics community. The aim was to collaboratively identify challenges associated with exascale plasma simulations and strategize on effective approaches to address them. We plan to replicate this initiative at ISC2024 and build on the success of the first BoF.

Figure 7: Tweet/Post of Plasma-PEPSC BoF at ISC2023 with discussions in three working groups.

5 Training: Code Camp & Webinars

The first Plasma-PEPSC Summer Camp took place on September 28th and 29th at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia (see Figure 8). This Plasma-PEPSC code camp aimed to provide participants with an understanding of Particle-in-Cell (PIC) codes and their exascale capabilities. The code camp topics included code building and installation procedures, input/output mechanisms, logging practices, performance measurement, code testing features, and discussions on specific PIC codes. Important sections included a crash course on co-designing with the EPI vector RISC-V accelerator, a demonstration on load balancing, and insights into I/O workflows with openPMD.

Figure 8: First Plasma-PEPSC code camp organized at the University of Ljubljana, Slovenia.

In addition, Plasma-PEPSC started a series of Webinars showcasing important technologies, and softwares developed in the project. The first webinar was scheduled on December 11 for presenting the new MPI features (investigated in Plasma-PEPSC WP3) of interest to the Plasma-PEPSC applications.

6 Exploitation

The Plasma-PEPSC code owners, including IPP CAS with BIT, MPG with GENE, HZDR with PIconGPU, and UoH with Vlasiator, are committed to leveraging the significant advancements achieved by Plasma-PEPSC in terms of performance and portability. This effort aims to enhance community adoption and foster collaborations with European agencies, initiatives such as EURATOM, EuroFusion, and ESA, as well as various national and international research communities.

Notably, SIPEARL, as the primary industrial partner for Plasma-PEPSC, plays a pivotal role in advancing the EU's strategy for improved autonomy and sovereignty in High-Performance Computing (HPC). Recognized at the European level, SIPEARL is integral to the EU HPC ecosystem encompassing intellectual property (IPR), hardware (HW), and software (SW). Collaboration involves working closely with SIPEARL processors and state-of-the-art accelerators within the project timeframe.

Academic partners, including KTH, TUM, UoH, and UL, will focus on exploiting their contributions through academic channels such as seminars and courses based on their work. Additionally, they aim to expand their network between industry and academia in Europe, engage in research projects to facilitate technology transfer to European industries and SMEs, and contribute to standardization bodies such as MPI.

HPC and Research Centers (MPG, BSC, FORTH, HZDR, and IPP CAS) will strategically address plasma simulation optimizations crucial for their HPC system users. The anticipated scientific publications resulting from their research endeavors will not only improve their academic standing but also initiate new collaborations.

7 Conclusion

WP6 activities in 2023 can be summarized as follows:

- We generated project website (more than 3000 visits in 2023), opened twitter account (15 posts in 2023).
- We had over 20+ Plasma-PEPSC Executive bi-weekly meetings and 2 Face-To-Face Project member bi-yearly meetings.
- We participated, and took part in, over 7 large international conferences in HPC and fusion plasma physics with more than 10 contributions.
- We organized a Face-To-Face Code Camp for code owners and user training.
- We published four papers: [1, 2, 3, 4] with others currently under review.

Based on these numbers, we can conclude that WP6 activities are well in agreement with project objectives and WP6-related milestones. We can also identify the following weak points require attention in 2024: the average number of twitter posts is expected to be 36 per year; we had to have one press release in 2023.

References

- [1] Jeremy J. Williams, David Tskhakaya, Stefan Costea, Ivy B Peng, Marta Garcia-Gasulla, and Stefano Markidis. Leveraging HPC Profiling & Tracing Tools to Understand the Performance of Particle-in-Cell Monte Carlo Simulations. *Euro-Par 2023: Parallel Processing Workshops: Euro-Par 2023 International Workshops, Limassol, Cyprus, August 28–September 1. Limassol, Cyprus: Springer Nature, arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.16512*, 2023.
- [2] Jennifer Faj, Jeremy J Williams, Ivy Bo Peng, Urs Ganse, Markus Battarbee, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Leo Kotipalo, Minna Palmroth, and Stefano Markidis. Mpi performance analysis in vlsiator: Unraveling communication bottlenecks. In *SC23: The International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage, and Analysis*, 2023.
- [3] Jennifer Faj, Ivy Peng, Jacob Wahlgren, and Stefano Markidis. Quantum computer simulations at warp speed: Assessing the impact of gpu acceleration. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.14860*, 2023.
- [4] Stefano Markidis. Enabling quantum computer simulations on amd gpus: a hip backend for google’s qsim. In *Proceedings of the SC’23 Workshops of The International Conference on High Performance Computing, Network, Storage, and Analysis*, pages 1478–1486, 2023.